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Transformations in(to) vocational identity among Norwegian VET students and apprentices learning in school and at work

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Abstract

This paper address the development of vocational identity in the Norwegian Vocational education and training, with data from the MECVET Project which is a large-scale empirical study of the development of vocational competences in three professions, healthcare, electronics and industrial mechanics.. The following research question is explored: How do contextual frame factors of the Norwegian VET model influence the development of the vocational identity of VET students and apprentices in transitions from school to work? The empirical foundation for this comes from a context survey in which central findings are identified. Respondents with strong vocational identities show a substantial interest in the further development of their own professional competence in their chosen professions. The most substantial transformation in the vocational identity development took place in the transitions from school-based to work-based learning, with learner autonomy and increased professional judgement being key aspects, as well as particular traits in the Norwegian VET model, namely tripartite cooperation and high degree of skilled worker's autonomy.

Keywords

vocational education and training; vocational competence development; vocational identities and cultures

1 Introduction

Learning and training for skilled work is subsequently a process of learning and becoming someone else in a process of vocational identity formation, not only in competence development, but also in knowing how to perform skilled work at the workplace. This includes learning to navigate the cultural codes, and sometimes the hardships of learning at the workplace (Collin, Paloniemi, Virtanen, & Eteläpelto, 2008). This paper explores how VET students and apprentices in a Norwegian context learn and develop vocational identity, in the context of the MECVET Project (Measuring Competence Development in Vocational Education and Training) piloting the COMET model (Rauner, Heinemann, & Hauschildt, 2013) in a Norwegian context.

Vocational education and training in Norway follows a two-plus-two sequential model; the first two years are in school, followed by two years of apprenticeship in enterprises ending with a trade examination and a trade certificate (The Norwegian Directorate for Education and Training). The particulars of the different learning contexts from school to work provide us

with interesting transfer issues in applying vocational proficiency from school-based to work-based learning. The Norwegian sequential VET model implies substantial shifts in how the apprentices regard themselves and their own learning trajectories, and accordingly changes in their vocational identity in transitional learning from school to work (Reegård, 2015). Further, this also emphasizes the impact of learning contexts for VET students' and apprentices' vocational identity development. Boundary learning (Akkerman, 2011) is a key aspect, especially in studying the identity developments of the respondents in the transition of status from being a VET student to an apprentice, subsequently in changing the venues of learning from school to work.

The following research question explored in this paper is: How do contextual frame factors of the Norwegian VET model influence the development of the vocational identity of VET students and apprentices in transitions from school to work?

Contextual frame factors are defined as social, economic, policy and cultural codes that influence and structure vocational learning at boundaries between school and work (Johannesen, 2015). These boundaries will provide a discussion about the VET students' and apprentices' views on their competence development, aiming for a contribution about the role of learning contexts, and the role of vocational identity development in VET. Important factors are that these VET students and apprentices have often made early career choices which impact their identity development through the various stages in vocational learning from school to work (Hvitved, 2014).

2 Theoretical perspectives: Vocational identity development

Developing a vocational identity is central to young people having made an early vocational career choice, as well as emerging vocational competency and a cultural affiliation to the selected profession, as *vocational becomings* developing a vocational habitus (Colley, James, Diment, & Tedder, 2003; Collin et al., 2008).

Vocational identity development in the MECVET context can be compared to that of model for competence development, drawing a line from the Dreyfus and Dreyfus (1980) model of a five-stage development of skills acquisition, in which novices improve through encounters with practical learning at the workplace taught by a teacher or instructor (Dreyfus & Dreyfus, 1980). Rauner et al (2011:32) argue that growing a vocational identity is a prerequisite for taking the professional role of an expert. The "from novice to expert" metaphor is accordingly aligned to the foundations in the COMET model, which draws on the concepts espoused by the competence model of Dreyfus and Dreyfus, but in a manner comprising eight dimensions from which the competence development is measured (Rauner, Heinemann, Maurer, & Haasler, 2011).

Transformations of vocational identities in boundary VET learning from school to work are discussed in the context of the impact of cultural factors in the assessment of vocational competencies. The major breaks in the respondents' identity development might be related to their transitions and boundary crossing in changing learning contexts from learning in school to work-based learning (Fejes & Köpsén, 2012). In addition, vocational identity development can be regarded as an ongoing process, in which the VET students and apprentices engage in a reflexive process of negotiating developments on the inside, in the self, with an outside influence in a structural developmental leap influenced by the workplace as the new learning context of the apprentices (Alvesson & Robertson, 2015).

The MECVET context questionnaire related to the respondents' vocational identity is analyzed through the COMET model's emphasis on occupational commitment in VET competence. The respondents in the study express vocational identity transformations in the status change experienced by crossing boundaries in becoming apprentices, seen as aligned to the

classic perspective of Erikson in identity development in the life stage theory of moving from adolescence to young adults (Erikson, 1968).

3 Methodology

The data in the study is from the MECVET project, which is a feasibility study testing the holistic assessment of vocational competence in Norway (Lahn & Nore, 2019, in press). The MECVET project is testing the German COMET model (Rauner et al., 2013) in the context of Norwegian VET at three stages of vocational education and training: 1. Second-year students in school-based VET; 2. First-year apprentices and 3. Second (and final)-year apprentices. The data are case-based test solutions written by respondents, and the study sample is N=458.

All the testees were asked to participate in an additional web-based context survey in all three years of the empirical study, in which the response rate was 95%. Here, the scope of the data analysis are the results of the web-based context survey. Measuring and assessing vocational competency is a complex procedure (Baethge et al., 2009). The discussion concerns how VET students and apprentices regard their own competence development, including vocational and identity development.

4 Results

Items in the context survey were related to the following areas of VET: 1. Questions related to the respondents' backgrounds, their education and the school or enterprise; 2. Questions concerning the MECVET case test just taken and 3. Questions related to attitudes towards work and profession.

The main findings in the context survey are that the respondents expressed their vocational identity as an evolving process when they change from school-based to work-based learning. The development of vocational identities of the respondents were expressed through open-ended replies on the survey context. The variables associated with vocational identity in our operationalization of the study through the survey were particularly related to occupational commitment, frame factors and transformations from school to work.

The survey may support further analysis of test results in three areas:

1. Factors related to the actual **testing situation** (time used and students' interest in participating in the test);
2. Factors related to **vocational identity** – like further education plans and interests of importance for the development of vocational qualifications as Health Care Workers or Industrial Mechanics. At the same time, it may also say something about their engagement and interest in solving the test-task (motivation); and
3. Factors related to the **framework conditions** for developing trade - specific qualifications at the Vg2 level of education. It may say something about students' preconditions for solving the tasks.

The findings can be summed up in the following manner:

- Respondents with strong vocational identities show a substantial interest in the further development of their own professional competence in the chosen professions in the MECVET study.
- Motivation and interest in the profession of choice were significant variables for the development of vocational identity.

- Plans related to future specific professional career- and life goals also proved to have an impact on vocational identity development, particularly among the apprentices in the study sample.
- Independence and the exercising of professional judgement at the workplace can be seen as prerequisites and conditions for enabling learner autonomy and growth for apprentices in work-based learning.
- Competencies evolve throughout the three years of the study:
 - Cultural factors in the assessment of vocational competencies: trade-specific, regional differences, vocational identity development and motivation
- The impact of cultural, contextual learning at the workplace:
 - “My colleagues are supportive”
 - “I have someone to ask questions”
- The impact of social background variables:
 - “My father has worked in this profession”
- Norwegian apprenticeship training offices “bridging the gap” (Nore & Lahn, 2014).
- The learning constraints and opportunities of work-based learning (Collin et al. 2008, Billett, 2004).
- Boundary learning: Development of vocational identity and cultural codes of learning at work, depending on variables related to work environment, support from training officers and colleagues, but also related to social background variables.
- Literacy and vocational competency: the written tests by the respondents suggest weaker writing competences in expressing their vocational competency than practical task oriented proficiency (Hellne-Halvorsen, Nore, & Lahn, 2019, in press).

5 Discussion

The ideal of the autonomous skilled worker aiming for the development of a holistic understanding of vocational skills and knowledge also entails a new vocational didactics suited for the complexity of vocational cultures (Jørgensen, 2009). Following the COMET model, this argument regarding vocational autonomy is also reflected in MECVET test tasks, solutions and the context survey (Rauner et al., 2011). Furthermore, the vocational practices of electronics use instrumental measurements as core frame factors. This contrasts the written culture in the vocational learning in health care, in which apprentices are accustomed to writing case-based solutions from early school-based VET (Mauroux et al., 2016).

The entrepreneurial thinking and the role of the creativity dimension in COMET are also related to vocational pedagogies and tools for VET, although these are not found in the Norwegian performance-based VET assessment culture (Rauner et al., 2013). Perspectives in vocational cultures that must be taken into account are teamwork and collaboration at the workplace, with a newer emphasis on the importance of developing generic skills, transversal skills and core competences in VET (Nägele & Stalder, 2018).

In Norway, there are also vast regional differences among professions such as electricians working offshore and on vessels on the west coast, and electricians working mostly on cabins and private houses in the eastern part of the country, and is reflected in the Norwegian MECVET-tasks. The gender divide in VET, including the Norwegian labor market, can be seen as another perspective that must be taken into account in discussing vocational identity (Hegna, 2017; Vagle & Møller, 2014). Gender, class and diversity measures should also be included in analyzing transformative identity development in work-based learning in VET, in

the context of the frame factors supplied in a Nordic social democracy with tripartite cooperation and social inclusion.

National VET traditions set a cultural framework for vocational learning and cultural development and vocational identity formation among youth, as well as in the development of competency, with local variations in enterprise and trade-specific working cultures. The expression for the development of a vocational habitus and vocational identity depends on motivation, background and how the workplace facilitate for learning in order for this learning environment at work to be expansive or restrictive (Fuller & Unwin, 2003).

As argued by Billett (2009), frame factors and conditions for supervised work-based learning in VET should comprise systematic guided learning in order to develop learner epistemologies (Billett, 2009). Facilitating for vocational didactics in work-based learning can entail that learning experiences that are not necessarily positive can add to practices fit for vocational learning (Billett, 2015). Developing vocational professional competence is many faceted and requires not only profession-specific skills and knowledge, but also includes the vocational didactics dimensions in the frame factors surrounding VET, in bridging the gaps between learning in school and at work (Nore & Lahn, 2014). These vocational didactics, including outcome orientation, cultural-historical embedding, and structures that are historical, temporal, vertical and horizontal, will certainly be subject to transitions due to the ever-changing nature of work (Gessler & Moreno Herrera, 2015).

The pulls, pushes and challenges of youth culture in knowledge society should be discussed in comparison to vocational cultures and the hardships of work. In order to become someone in vocational becoming and learning, you have to be someone in identity development. In this way, we will obtain new data and a deeper understanding of how contextual frame factors affect youth recruitment to VET, vocational identity development and subsequently future VET learning cultures.

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